

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF NAIL LACQUER WITH CISSUS QUADRANGULARIS EXTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Naill acquer is a cosmetic preparation which is used to provide elegant look to the nails and also beautify it. An attempt was made to prepare transparent nail lacquer containing natural antifungal agent obtained from extract of whole plant of cissus quadrangularis. Cissus quadrangularis is a perenninal herbaceous plant belongs to vitaceae family. The extract of cissus quadrangularis was evaluated for antifungal study against candida albicans by Agar well diffusion method. Minimum inhibitory concentration of extract against candida albicans was performed to get the amount of extract to be loaded in the nail lacquer. Nail lacquer was prepared by using nitrocellulose (which act as a film forming agent, the film formed by nitrocellulose are hard, tough and waterproof and also resist abrasion), ethyl cellulose (it also act as a film

forming agent like nitrocellulose, the coating films of ethylcellulose have good glossiness and excellent slickening capability and flexibility), ethylacetate (it is used to dissolve other substances including nitrocellulose, the basic film forming materials in nailpolish), salicylic acid (salicylic acid act as a permeation enhancer in the preparation of nail lacquer), dibutyl phthalate (it is the plasticizer used in the preparation of nail lacquer, it imparts flexibility, gloss, adhesion to nail and reduce it tendency to shrink), extract of cissus quadrangularis (antifungal agent), acetone (it act as a solvent in nail lacquer)with continuous stirring. Formulations of nail lacquer were evaluated for drying time, gloss, non volatilir content, water resistance, smoothness of flow. Drying time of formulation was 75sec with visually seen glossiness of formulation. Formulation of naillacquer showed good non-volatile content, water resistance and viscosity with smoothness of flow. Antifungal activity of nail lacquer

formation prepared with cissus quadrangularis against candida albicans was found good (zone of inhibition : 12 mm). The formulation at laboratory scale was done and evaluated for number of parameters to ensure its safety and efficacy.

KEYWORDS: Nail lacquer, Nitrocellulose, Ethylcellulose, Salicylic acid, Ethyl acetate, Dibutyl phthalate, Acetone.

INTRODUCTION

The nail lacquers are the largest and most important group of manicure preparations. It is also known as nail enamel or nail varnish. The products can vary from transparent uncoloured to once highly favoured pale pink to present day vivid shades. The application of nail lacquers covers the nail with a water and air impermeable to membrane which remains for days and normally can be removed only by suitable solvent.

A good nail lacquer should have the following properties:

- It should be harmless to the skin and nails.
- It should be convenient and easy to apply.
- It should be stable on storage.
- It should form a satisfactory film on nails.

To achieve a satisfactory film it should have the following characteristics:

- It should have proper viscosity and good wetting and flow properties so that the film formed is even.
- It should have uniform colour production.
- It should have good gloss.
- It should have good adhesive properties.
- It should have sufficient flexibility so that it does not crack or become brittle.
- It should have sufficient hard surface which is resistant to impact and scratch.
- It should have reasonable drying time without developing bloom.
- Long maintenance of the film character.^[8]

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Cissusquadrangularis extract

Nitrocellulose

Ethylcellulose

Salicylic acid

Ethyl acetate

Dibutyl phthalate

Acetone.

METHOD OF PREPARATION

1. Nitrocellulose and ethyl cellulose were dissolved in sufficient quantity of ethyl acetate to get clear solution.
2. Salicylic acid was dissolved in above mixture and dibutyl phthalate was added.
3. Then extract of *C. quadrangularis* and acetone were added with continuous stirring at 100 rpm on magnetic stirrer.
4. Finally, sufficient quantity of ethyl acetate was added to get proper consistency to nail lacquer

EXTRACTION METHOD

The air dried plant of *Cissus quadrangularis* were powdered and passed through 20 mesh sieve. 10g of plant powder were weighed and was extracted with 20ml of chloroform using Soxhlet apparatus with temperature maintained for extraction was 55°C. The duration of Soxhlet extraction was 3-4 hours. The extract were concentrated by pouring them into clean round bottom flask and were allowed for evaporation of solvents by using distillation apparatus. Then the concentrated crude extract was stored at 40°C in air tight bottle until further use.

FORMULATION

SL. NO	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3
1	Nitrocellulose(%)	2	2	2
2	Ethylcellulose(%)	1	1	1
3	Salicylic acid(%)	0.3	0.5	0.6
4	Dibutyl phthalate(%)	0.5	0.5	0.5
5	Ethyl acetate(%)	0.2	0.2	0.2
6	Acetone(%)	0.1	0.1	0.1
7	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> (mg)	0.25	0.5	1

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

1. **Smoothness to flow:** The sample was poured on a glass plate and was inclined vertically.

2. **Colour:** comparing with master color standard by applying on thumbnails, holding them side by side moving the thumb with the standard first on the right and then left.

3. **Gloss:** The sample was uniformly applied over the nail. The gloss was visually compared with the marketed cosmetic nail lacquer.

4. **Drying time:** The formulation was applied on a glass slide and was allowed to dry. The drying time was analysed until the film was dry to touch.

5. **Hardness:** This is the measure of the hardness of the film. Hardness was evaluated after apply nail polish on nail and apply external pressure by hand on it.^[46]

6. **Non volatile Content:** Sample measuring was poured into a glass petri plate and the weight was noted. The plate was then placed in the oven at 105 °C for 1 hour. The weight of the plate was noted for 1 hour.

$$\text{Percentage non volatile content} = \frac{\text{Initial weight (W1)} - \text{Final weight(w2)}}{\text{Initial weight(W1)}} \times 100$$

7. **Viscosity:** Viscosity of the formulation were analyzed using Brookfield Viscometer.

8. **Grittiness:** The product was checked for the presence of any gritty particles by applying it on the nail.

9. Water resistance: This is the measure of the resistance towards water permeability of the film. This was done by applying a continuous film on a surface and immersing it in water. The weight before and after immersion was noted and increase in weight was calculated. Higher the increase in weight lowers the water resistance.

10. Peel adhesion test by texture analysis: A peel adhesion test for formulations was performed by Texture Analyzer. Nail lacquer (0.1 g) was applied onto a surface of plate with the help of brush and allowed to dry for 10 min at room temperature. An adhesive tape was applied on it. The other end of tape was fixed at adapter probe. The strength of adhesion between lacquer film and plate became decided via measuring force required to peel lacquer film off the plate the using of adhesive tape. Time and load required for peeling off lacquer is recorded.

11. Lacquer film thickness: 1ml of formulation was spread equally with an applicator brush in 8cm diameter petridish and was allowed to dry at room temperature. After drying nail lacquer film was isolated from the petri dish. The film thickness was measured at three different places using a micrometer screw gauge and average was calculated.^[47]

ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY

Formulation was tested for Antifungal activity by Agar well diffusion method.

Medium used :Potato Dextrose Agar Medium (1L)

Culture of test organisms: Growth of culture adjusted according to McFarland Standard, 0.5%

- Candida albicans (ATCC 10231)

Standard antifungal agent: Clotrimazole (concentration: 10mg / ml).

PROCEDURE

Potato Dextrose agar plates were prepared and overnight grown species of fungus, Candida albicans were swabbed. Wells of approximately 10mm was bored using a well cutter and samples of different concentrations such as 250µg, 500µg and 1000µg were added. The zone of inhibition was measured after overnight incubation at room temperature and compared with that of standard antimycotic (Clotrimazole) (NCCLS, 1993).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

SL. NO	PARAMETER	RESULT		
		F1	F2	F3
1`	Gloss	Good	Good	Good

2	Drying Time	90sec	85sec	75 sec
3	Non volatile content	33%	35%	36%
4	Water resistance	86%	83%	90 %
5	Thickness of film	0.17 mm	0.17mm	0.19mm

ANTIFUNGAL EVALUATION

The antifungal activity of extract was performed against *C. albicans*. The extract 1000 μ g showed the highest zone of inhibition (12 mm), while 500 μ g showed no zone of inhibition.

Sample	Concentration (μ g)	Zone of inhibition (mm)
Cissus quadrangularis extract	Clotrimazole(100 μ g)	28
	250	Nil
	500	Nil
	1000	12
Sample	Concentration (μ g)	Zone of inhibition (mm)
Nail lacquer	Clotrimazole(100 μ g)	28
	250	Nil
	500	Nil
	1000	11

Zone of inhibition of Cissus quadrangularis extract and Cissus quadrangularis extract loaded nail Lacquer.

CONCLUSION

The use of natural extracts as active ingredients has improved the use of cosmetics. Usefulness of herbs in the cosmetic production has been extensively increased in personnel care system and there is a great demand for the herbal cosmetics. The nail lacquer formulations were prepared with Cissus quadrangularis using simple mixing method. The permeability of the formulation was enhanced by using the permeation enhancer (Salicylic acid). Solvent evaporation occurs when the product is applied to the nail plate. After the solvent has evaporated, the film ie, produced by film forming agents like nitrocellulose &

ethyl cellulose is left behind. The study reveals that the developed nail polish with *Cissus quadrangularis* extract was comparatively better than other formulations because of its antifungal activity. Our study is mainly focussed on the antifungal activity using *Candida albicans* in which the formulation shows highest activity. Based on physical evaluation formulated nail polish, showed good appearance, consistency, drying time, excellent spreadibility and smoothness. *Cissus quadrangularis* extract loaded nail lacquer was successfully delivered through nail plate. The incorporation of penetration enhancer salicylic acid proved to enhance transungual delivery. Apart from treating the nail infections, the nail lacquers can be also used for beautification of nails with ease of application. F3 formulation met all the evaluation parameters and selected as the best formulation. *Cissus quadrangularis* showed good anti fungal activity thus it was considered as a good choice as an anti fungal agent.

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